

Programme

MONDAY 3 MAY

09:30 to 15:30 : Pre-conference Workshop - IVS3D / ESRI : The use and benefits of the integrated application of Fledermaus and ArcGIS in Habitat Mapping	
17:00	Geohab 2010 Icebreaker and Registration
19:00	End of day

TUESDAY 4 MAY

08:30	Mihimihi (Traditional Maori Welcome)
08:40	Opening and Welcome
09:00	Keynote address: Andy Wheeler An Atlas of Ireland's Deep-water Seabed: the preview
09:30	Session 1 - Mapping metrics (Chair. Brian Todd)
10:10	Morning Tea
10:50	Session 1 - Mapping metrics, cont. (Chair. Vaughan Stagpoole)
12:30	Lunch
13:30	Session 1 - Mapping metrics, cont. (Chair. David Bowden)
15:10	Afternoon Tea
15:40	Session 1 - Mapping metrics, cont. (Chair. Andrew Heap)
17:00	Break
17:10	Special Meeting: Glossary (Chair. Mark Costello)
17:40	Special Session (S6): ATLAS (Chair. Peter Harris)
19:00	End of day

WEDNESDAY 5 MAY

08:30	Keynote address: Xavier Lurton Credibility of Sonar Backscatter Strength measurement, modelling and inversion
09:00	Session 2 - Statistical Analysis (Chair. Vanessa Lucieer)
10:20	Morning Tea
10:50	Session 2 - Statistical Analysis, cont. (Chair. Vladimir Kostylev)
12:30	Lunch
13:30	Session 2 - Statistical Analysis, cont. (Chair. Ian Wright)
13:50	Session 3 - Geo-Bio Interaction (Chair. Ian Wright)
15:10	Afternoon Tea
15:40	Session 3 - Geo-Bio Interaction, cont. (Chair. Judi Hewitt)
17:20	Break
18:30	Barbecue
22:00	End of day

THURSDAY 6 MAY

08:30	Keynote address: Malcolm Clark Habitat as a proxy for biodiversity: how can seamount classification systems aid the scientific design of marine protected areas
09:00	Session 3 - Geo-Bio Interaction, cont. (Chair. Bernard Pelletier)
10:20	Morning Tea
10:50	Session 4 - Vulnerable Habitat (Chair. Miquel Canals)
12:30	Lunch
13:30	Session 5 - National Programmes (Chair. Nic Bax)
15:10	Afternoon Tea
15:40	Session 5 - National Programmes, cont. (Chair. Gary Greene)
16:40	Break
17:10	Wrap-up discussion - AGM
18:10	End of day

FRIDAY 7 MAY

07:50 to 18:00 : Field Trip Discover faults, rocks, food and wine	
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